

EXTRACTION OF NATTOKINASE ENZYME FROM *Pseudomonas* spp. ISOLATED FROM GOAT MILK AND EVALUATION OF THROMBOLYTIC ACTIVITY *IN VITRO*

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ABSTRACT

The present study was carried out to extract nattokinase enzyme from *Pseudomonas* spp. isolated from goat milk and to evaluate thrombolytic activity of the isolated enzyme in blood samples. In this investigation, selective media Cetrimide agar was used to isolate *Pseudomonas* spp. from goat milk. *Pseudomonas* spp. was used for nattokinase production using different production media. The partially purified enzyme's activity was determined. The enzyme was then subjected to thrombolytic activity to evaluate its potential on lysis of blood clots. The morphological and biochemical tests inferred the presence of *Pseudomonas* spp. The activity of the enzyme nattokinase produced from the isolate was found to be 1020U/ml with molecular weight of 27KDa. The enzyme isolated was found to have thrombolytic potential.

Keywords: Goat milk, Identification of bacteria, *Pseudomonas* spp., Nattokinase enzyme, SDS-PAGE, Thrombolytic activity.

INTRODUCTION

The development of a blood clot (partial or total blockage) in venous or arterial blood vessels, which restricts blood flow and causes clinical consequences known as thrombosis [1]. Fibrin clots build up in blood vessels, causing thrombosis and ultimately cardiovascular disease. [2]. Myocardial infarction (AMI) is now treated with thrombolytic therapy, a conventional approach. However, there are currently issues with clinically prescribed thrombolytic drugs, including delayed effects and other side effects like bleeding, re-occlusion, etc. [3]. According to estimates from the World Health Organization, one person worldwide dies from this condition every six seconds. The risk is far higher than that of cancer, which is one of the main causes of death for humans. *Pseudomonas* spp. are Gram-negative, aerobic, non-spore-forming, motile rods that measure 0.5 to 1 μm by 2 to 7 μm and have one or more polar flagella for swimming motility. The genus *Pseudomonas* belongs to the Pseudomonadaceae family [4]. The single-chain protein nattokinase (NK), which is produced by *Bacillus subtilis*, has a molecular weight of 20 KDa and a pH of 8.6 [5]. As of now, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus licheniformis*, *Bacillus amyloliquefaciens*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and other bacteria are known to produce NK [6]. Milk microbiological analysis revealed the presence of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Pseudomonas* spp. produce extracellular proteolytic and lipolytic enzymes during their growth in raw milk and these enzymes remain active after the milk is pasteurized, or otherwise heat-treated. [7].

MATERIALS AND METHOD

ISOLATION OF *Pseudomonas* spp. FROM GOAT MILK SAMPLE

Milk samples from goats were collected and stored in the refrigerator at 4°C until analysis was done. The sample was diluted to 10^{-6} . [8] and inoculated in the cetrimide agar media. *Pseudomonas* spp. was isolated using cetrimide agar media using standard procedure [9].

Fig:1. Pure culture of *Pseudomonas* spp.

IDENTIFICATION OF BACTERIA

GRAM STAINING

Took a clean, grease free slide. Prepared the smear of suspension on the clean slide with a loop full of samples. Air dried, heat fixed and Crystal Violet was poured and kept for about 30 seconds to 1 minute and rinsed with water. Flooded the gram's iodine for 1 minute and washed with water. Then, washed with 95% alcohol or acetone for about 10-20 seconds and rinsed with water. Added Safranin for about 1 minute and washed with water. Air dried, blot dried and observed under the microscope [10].

SPORE STAINING

Prepared a smear of the *Pseudomonas* spp. air-dried and heat-fixed. Put a beaker of water on the hot plate and boiled until steam was coming up from the water and then turned the hot plate down so that the water was barely boiling. Placed the wire stain rack over the beaker which then had steam coming up from the boiled water. Cut a small piece of paper towel and placed it on top of the smear on the slide. The towel will prolong the time that the dye is in contact with the bacterial walls by preventing it from evaporating too quickly. Flooded the smear with the primary dye, malachite green, and left for 5 minutes. Kept the paper towel moist with the malachite green. Don't let the dye dry on the towel. Removed and discarded the small paper towel piece. Washed with water, moved the slide and transferred to stain tray to end up the last step in the protocol. Placed the smear in the stain jar or flooded the smear with the counterstain dye, safranin, and left for 1 minute. Washed well with water, blot dried and observed under the microscope [11].

BIOCHEMICAL TEST

INDOLE PRODUCTION TEST

In this test, the organism under consideration was grown in peptone water broth. The broth was sterilized for 15 minutes at around 121°C. To test the broth for Indole production, Kovac's reagent was added. A positive result was indicated by a red layer forming on top of the liquid [12].

METHYL RED TEST

Two loopful of the appropriate bacterial culture were added to the broth aseptically. For 48–72 hours, the test tubes were incubated at 37°C. Added a few drops of methyl red indicator to the tubes that were being incubated and observed the results [13].

VOGES-PROSKAUER TEST

Added a pure culture of the test organism to a tube of VP broth for inoculation. Incubated at 35°C for a full day. Finally, aliquot one milliliter of broth into a sterile test tube. Added 0.2 ml of 40% KOH after adding 0.6 ml of 5% α -naphthol. After giving the tube, a gentle shake to expose the medium to oxygen in the atmosphere, let it sit undisturbed for ten to fifteen minutes [14].

CITRATE TEST

Gently touched a colony that was 18 to 24 hours with the tip of a needle to inoculate it with simmon citrate agar on the slant. Loosely fitted the cap onto the tube. Aerobic incubation took place for 18 to 24 hours at 35°C. Noted the slant's development of a blue hue, which indicates alkalization [12].

OXIDASE TEST

Oxidase test which was incorporated with tetramethyl-p-phenylene-diamine dihydrochloride was taken in a petridish. The colony to be tested was picked up with a sterile loop and smeared over a moist area. The change in colour of the disc was noted [15].

CATALASE TEST

Used a sterile loop to transfer a small amount of colony growth to the surface of a cleaned, dried glass slide. Placed a drop of 3% H₂O₂ in the glass slide. Observed for the evolution of oxygen bubbles [16].

CARBOHYDRATE FERMENTATION TEST

Different peptone broth media were made for each of the four sugars: mannitol, lactose, sucrose, and glucose. To 100 ml of medium, 1.2 ml of phenol red 0.2% solution was added. Test tubes were filled with 5 milliliters of medium containing indicator. Durham's tubes were very carefully placed inside the test tube so that no bubbles formed. The medium-containing test tubes were sanitized. After being cooled, the sterilized tubes received an inoculation of test culture. The next day, the alterations were noted [17].

TRIPLE SUGAR IRON TEST

After preparing and pouring the TSI agar medium into the test tube, it was autoclaved at 121°C to sterilize it. After the slant was formed, touch the top of a well-isolated colony with a sterilized straight inoculation needle. Cooled in a slanted position to give a butt and a slant. Inoculated TSI agar by streaking on the agar slant's surface after first piercing through the medium's center to the tube's bottom. For 18 to 24 hours, the tube was incubated at 35°C with the cap loose [18].

PRODUCTION OF NATTOKINASE ENZYME

Three different media were used for enzyme production. Media 1 includes 100 ml of nutrient broth, 2 includes production medium (1% crab shell, 0.1% KH₂PO₄, 0.05% MgSO₄, pH-7 at 37°C), and 3 includes nutrient broth (Hi-Media) with 0.1% crab shell. Each media was inoculated with 1% seed inoculum. The media were then incubated for 24 hours at 37°C in a shaker spinning at 120 rpm. The crude enzyme was extracted by centrifuging the medium for 10 minutes at 10,000 rpm [19].

PARTIAL PURIFICATION OF ENZYME

Placed sample into an external chamber of the dialysis buffer (with gentle stirring of the buffer). Dialyzed for 2-4 hours at room temperature. Changed the dialysis buffer and dialyzed for another 2-4 hours. Changed the dialysis buffer and dialyzed overnight at 4°C [20].

DETERMINATION OF PROTEIN CONTENT

The protein content of partially purified enzyme extract was evaluated using Lowry's method.

DETERMINATION OF ENZYME ACTIVITY BY CASEIN DIGESTION ASSAY

To measure the nattokinase activity, 0.1 mL of partially purified enzyme, 0.7 mL of 0.1 M sodium phosphate buffer, and 0.1 mL of 2% casein were incubated for five minutes at room temperature. Centrifuged the mixture at 8,000 rpm for 10 minutes, stopped the reaction after adding 0.1 ml of 1.5 M trichloroacetic acid (TCA). At 560 nm, the absorbance of the supernatant was calculated. A unit of caseinolytic activity (U) was defined as the amount of enzyme that released 1 μ m of tyrosine equivalent per minute, or 1 M of tyrosine equivalent per minute [21].

CHARACTERIZATION OF PARTIALLY PURIFIED ENZYME

The molecular mass and purity of the partially purified enzyme were assessed using sodium dodecyl sulphate polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE), with 4% acrylamide used in the stacking gel and 12% acrylamide in the separating gel. Using Coomassie R 250 brilliant blue stain and standard as a protein ladder, protein bands were visualized [22].

THROMBOLYTIC ASSAY

Three sterile 500 μ l microcentrifuge tubes containing venous blood from healthy volunteers were incubated for 45 minutes at 37°C. Each tube containing a clot was weighed once more to ascertain the clot weight after the serum was fully removed following clot formation. The clots in each micro centrifuge tube were appropriately labeled, and 100 μ l of crude enzyme and precipitated enzyme made of ammonium sulfate were added to the test tubes. After 90 minutes of incubation at 37°C, clot lysis was checked in each tube. Following clot disruption and incubation, the obtained fluid was removed and the tubes were weighed once more. The

percentage of clot lysis was calculated from the obtained weight difference measured before and after clot lysis [23].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

IDENTIFICATION OF *Pseudomonas* spp. FROM GOAT MILK

GRAM STAINING

The bacteria was observed as Gram negative, rod shaped occurring singly or in chains (Fig:2)

Fig:2. Gram staining

SPORE STAINING

The isolated bacterium was non spore forming. The result observed is shown in Fig:3.

Fig:3. Spore staining

BIOCHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS

Biochemical characteristics of the bacterial strain were determined by using various biochemical tests like carbohydrate test, catalase, MR-VP test, Indole test, TSI test and their results were recorded in the following Table 1.

Table 1: Biochemical characteristics of bacteria.

S.No	BIOCHEMICAL TEST	RESULT
1	Indole test	Positive
2	Methyl Red test	Negative
3	Voges-Proskauer test	Negative
4	Citrate test	Positive
5	Catalase test	Positive
6	Oxidase test	Positive
7	Triple Sugar Iron test	Negative
8	Glucose	Negative
9	Lactose	Negative
10	Sucrose	Negative
11	Mannitol	Positive

From biochemical tests, it is inferred that the organism was found to be *Pseudomonas* spp.

PARTIAL PURIFICATION OF ENZYME

For the production of nattokinase, *Pseudomonas* spp. isolated goat milk was utilized. The organism was cultured in 3 different media.

Media 1: Nutrient broth

Media 2: Production medium (Nutrient broth with 1% crab shell, 0.1% KH₂PO₄, 0.05% MgSO₄)

Media 3: Nutrient broth with 0.1% crab shell

DETERMINATION OF ENZYME ACTIVITY

The Casein Digestion Assay was used to measure the activity of nattokinase generated in three distinct media. The result is shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2: Nattokinase enzyme activity

S.NO	MEDIA	ENZYME ACTIVITY	PROTEIN CONC.
1	Nutrient broth	980 U/ml	2.1 mg/ml
2	Production medium	1020 U/ml	2.4 mg/ml
3	Nutrient broth+ Crab shell	1004 U/ml	2.3 mg/ml

CHARACTERIZATION OF PARTIALLY PURIFIED ENZYME

The partially purified Nattokinase was found to have a molecular weight of 27 KDa, which was consistent with the protein marker and banding pattern (Fig:4).

Fig:4. SDS PAGE of nattokinase

THROMBOLYTIC ASSAY

The results in Table 3 demonstrated the thrombolytic activity of Nattokinase extracted from *Pseudomonas* spp.

TABLE: 3 THROMBOLYTIC ACTIVITY

S. NO	Tube s	Weight of tube (a)	Weight of tube with clot (b)	Weight of clot b-a	Weight of tube with clot after lysis (d)	Weight of lysis (e) (b-d)	Percentage of clot lysis= weight of lysis÷weight of clot*100
1	A	1.0	1.40	0.4	1.40	0.4	0%
2	B	1.0	1.38	0.38	1.26	0.12	31.57%
3	C	1.0	1.39	0.39	1.25	0.14	35.89%

A: Control

B: Enzyme extracted from culture grown in production medium added into blood sample

C: Enzyme extracted from culture grown in nutrient broth with crab shell added into blood sample.

From the above table, it is evident that the nattokinase enzyme produced from *Pseudomonas* spp. was found to exhibit a maximum of 35.89 % thrombolytic activity.

CONCLUSION

The enzyme nattokinase, also known as fibrinolytic enzyme, was found to be produced by a variety of microorganisms, including algae, fungi, bacteria, and actinomycetes. The present study was carried out to extract Nattokinase enzyme from *Pseudomonas* spp. isolated from goat milk and to evaluate thrombolytic activity of the isolated enzyme in blood samples. The result inferred maximum activity of the enzyme nattokinase produced from the isolate was found to be 1020U/ml with molecular weight of 27KDa. The thrombolytic assay concluded that the enzyme exhibited 35.89 % clot lysis activity. Hence further study can be done to optimize the production of nattokinase enzymes and determine its extensive medical applications.

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